

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

UNVEILING THE POWER OF PLANTS: A REVIEW ON HERBAL SUNSCREENS

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 04/05/2024

Available online

05/06/2024

Keywords

SPF,
Ultraviolet Filters,
Photo-Protective,
Sunscreen,
Natural Sunscreen Agent.

ABSTRACT

Creating sunscreen cream formulations with a high sun protection factor (SPF) & desirable properties was the aim of this study. Skin conditions such as sunburn and the associated symptoms of extended exposure have been linked to ultraviolet (UV) radiation. Because of its capacity to reflect, absorb, and scatter UV light, sunscreens have shown to be helpful in lowering the prevalence of skin conditions such as sunburn, skin aging, and immune-suppression. The most common method these days for shielding our skin against them is to use sunscreen. Sunscreens are put through frequent testing and given a SPF (Sun Protection Factor) based on how well they shield skin. Due to their ability to induce leukocytosis, allergic reactions, damage DNA (deoxyribonucleic acid), reduce organ weight, and even cause anemia, the majority of synthetic sunscreen ingredients are extremely dangerous to humans.

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Please cite this article in press as **Mohammad Khalid** et al. Unveiling the Power of Plants: A Review on Herbal Sunscreens. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical research*.2024;14(05).

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INTRODUCTION

The ultraviolet-visible lights (UV-VIS), Infrared (IR) waves of solar radiation that strike the earth's surface are utilized^[1]. All electromagnetic wave falls within the range of 100 nm- 1 mm in spectrum, with UV radiation having the shortest wavelength (200–400 nm) compared to visible light (400–740 nm) and infrared radiation (760 nm –1,000,000 nm). About 10% of the sun's total light output is made up of UV rays. Three recommended ranges (UVA, UVB and UVC) comprise the broad spectrum of UV radiation. Within that range, UVA has the longest wavelength (320–400 nm) but the lowest energy photon, UVB is in the middle (280–320 nm), and UVC is the smallest (100–280 nm) but the highest energy^[2]. Moderate sun exposure has been shown to have several positive impacts, such as increased vitamin D production^[3], antibacterial activity^[4], and better cardiovascular health^[5, 6]. Nonetheless, prolonged exposure to UV radiation is thought to increase the risk of both acute & chronic eye damage as well as skin cancer^[7].

Fig. 1 Electromagnetic spectra solar ultra violet rays & their biological effect on skin^[2].

Sunscreen, commonly referred to as Sun block or sun-tanning lotion, is a topical sunscreen (photo protective) substance that helps prevent skin cancer by reflecting or absorbing part of the sun's ultraviolet (UV) rays^[8]. It also helps prevent sunburn. There are various types of sunscreen available for topical use, including lotion, gels, spray, foams (including whipped or expanded foam lotion), powders, sticks and more^[9]. Sunscreen is frequently used in addition to apparel, especially sunhats, sunglasses, and specially designed clothing that protects against the sun^[10]. Other forms of protection include umbrellas.

An example of a lotion, spray, or other topical treatment that helps protect the skin from UV radiation from the sun is herbal sunscreen lotion, which also lowers the risk of sunburn and other skin damage^[11]. According to there are two categories for sunscreen.

Physical Sun-screen

Chemical-based Sun-screen

Physical Sun-screen:

Those that let in sun light reflection. Physical sunscreens have inert mineral particles in them that act as a mirror to reflect UV radiation. Modern physical sunscreens reflect radiation in the UVB and short UVA regions better than older formulations because of the small sizes of the particle^[12].

Chemical-based Sunscreen:

Sunscreen agents are intended only for external usage; those that absorb UV rays should be avoided. The application of sunscreen as a photo-protectant to shield against UV radiation. Skin is primarily damaged by UV radiation through reactive oxygen species (ROS), which interact and alter proteins and lipids. UVA radiation has less of an impact on skin damage than UVB radiation^[13]. To effectively prevent photo-aging and skin cancer, sunscreen should also contain antioxidant agents in addition to sun block agents. Plants are a popular choice for sunscreen composition because of their antioxidant activity, which helps prevent skin damage from sun radiation^[14].

Sunscreen classification:

Based on how they are applied, sunscreen is categorized as systemic or topical. Topical sunscreen is further classified into two groups according to how they work as a barrier.

Organic Sun-screen

Inorganic Sun-screen

Organic Sun-screen:

Organic sunscreen absorbs UV radiation, which are then converted to heat, because it is thin and perfect for daily use, adding skincare components is simple. Chemically, organic sunscreen actives are carbon-based compounds. Its active ingredient is a single mineral^[15].

Inorganic Sunscreen:

These particles act as a physical shield against UV radiation, scattering and reflecting UV photons back into the surrounding area. They encompass the whole UV spectrum, which makes them broad spectrum. Another name for inorganic sunscreen is sun block^[16].

Selection of Sun-screen according to skin types:

Use a mild cleanser to help you wash your face. This will guarantee the removal of makeup, contaminants, and other debris. Make sure not to touch your face for an hour as you wait. Your skin type will become clearer once it has returned to its original form. Dab your face with tissue paper. You need to focus on the region that consists of your nose and forehead. Here's when using a tissue to wipe is advised.

The five different forms of skin are described here-

Normal Skin: Congratulations if your skin feels silky and soft, doesn't flake or reveal any oil! Your skin type is typical.

Oily Skin: If there is a lot of grease on your body you have an oily skin type if there is a lot of grease on the tissue paper. It is typical for you to have big pores and a shine.

Dry Skin: Your skin is dry if there are many flakes and dead skin cells on the tissue paper. It is advisable that you moisturize your skin.

Combination skin: Combination skin types listed above is referred to as mixture skin. Since most of you probably have this skin type, it's fairly common. Generally, your skin is dry in other areas and greasy on the forehead and nose^[17].

Sensitive skin: For fair-skinned individuals who burn easily, a broad spectrum sunscreen with a high SPF, such 40+, is recommended. If you have quickly tanned skin, you may want to use a broad spectrum sunscreen with an intermediate SPF, such 9–15+. You don't require sunscreen if you have darkly pigmented skin and don't have any issues with the sun or photosensitivity.

ADVANTAGES:

- Low cost
- Easily accessible ingredients
- Non-toxic and non-irritating
- Neutral;
- Heat-stable
- Simple to produce^[18].

DISADVANTAGES:

- The manufacturing process is labor-intensive and complex; it is challenging to conceal taste and odor.
- Compared to allopathic dosage forms, herbal medications have slower acting effects and necessitate prolonged treatment^[19].

APPLICATIONS:

- The FDA tests sunscreens at a dose of 2 mg per cm² of exposed skin^[20].
- Research indicates that the amount of sunscreen actually applied ranges from 20 to 50 percent of the recommended dosage for the specified SPF.
- The median quantity of sunscreen applied could be roughly calculated using diary registrations of the skin area; the results were 0.39 and 0.79 mg/cm², respectively.
- Research indicates that most customers only apply 1/4 to 1/2 of the recommended amount to meet the stated sun protection factor (SPF); hence, the effective SPF should be reduced to the square or fourth root of the number that is sold, accordingly^[21].
- The results of a follow-up research were more linear than predicted, showing a substantial exponential relationship between SPF and the quantity of sunscreen used^[22].
- Calculating the application thickness can be done simply by dividing the amount of sunscreen (in grams) by the area of skin treated with sunscreen (in centimeters squared)^[16].

SUN SPORT AND ADVANCES IN SUN-SCREENS:

- Nano sun-screen
- Children's sun-screen
- Roll-on sun-screen
- Spray sun-screen^[16].

NATURAL SUNSCREENS:**Aloe vera**

Aloe vera gel is made from the leaves of *A. barbadensis* and Aloe vera plants. Because aloe vera gel has a hydrating and renewing effect, it is frequently applied in cosmetics and toiletries. It preserves skin by blocking UVA and UVB rays. natural equilibrium of moisture Acemannan, a D-isomer mucopolysaccharide, stimulates the healing process and results in an increase in collagen and fibroblast synthesis. Due to their spectrophotometric peaks at approx. 297 nm, aloe extracts and aloin from the plant can be used as sunscreen on both skin and hair [23, 24 & 25].

The purpose of the study was to ascertain whether aloe vera juice had any photoprotective effects on chemically colored Asian hair, specifically black and grey. Measurements of tryptophan concentration showed that hair exposed to the elements and left untreated had more chemical damage, but hair treated with aloe vera juice provided protection from UV rays [26].

Fig 2: Aloe.

Tomato

The primary source of lycopene is tomato (*Lycopersicon-esculentum*) fruit, which is also being investigated for its antioxidant properties in the cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries. It is more than just a pigment; Strongly antioxidant, it fights oxygen-derived free radicals that reside underneath the lipid membrane and outermost layer of skin. Lycopene prevents lipid peroxidation, scavenges lipid radicals, and protects the skin from UV-induced erythema. Lycopene has the ability to lessen the damaging effects of UV radiation on skin and strengthen defenses against the short- and long-term (burns) and cancer-causing effects of sun exposure [27, 28 & 29].

Fig. 3: Tomato.

Pomegranate

Ellagitannins and anthocyanins, the primary antioxidant polyphenols, are found in pomegranate (*Punica granatum*) juice. The third commercial sun-screen treatment, Anti-stress-5001 (EnviroShield Products Co., USA), Surround1 (Ag Nova Tech., Australia), and Parasol1 (Crop Care, Australia), were also examined for effectiveness. Fruit was planted at Condobolin, New South Wales, Australia, to protect the pomegranate from sunburn. Results indicated that for the category of badly sunburned damaged fruit, sunscreen treatments had a significant benefit ($p = 0.05$). When comparing fruit treated with Surround1 (14.7%) and Parasol1 (12.8%) to the control fruit (25.8%), there was a statistically significant decrease in the percentage of fruits with substantial damage; however, the anti-stress 5501 (19%) did not have a meaningful effect [30, 31].

Figure 4: Pomegrana.

Green Tea

The *Camellia sinensis* plant's fresh leaves are needed to make green tea. It seems that the main mediators preventing chemotherapy are polyphenols. (-)-epicatechin (EC), (-)-epicatechin-3-gallate (ECG), (-)-epigallocatechin (EGC), and (-)-epigallocatechin-3-gallate (EGCG) are the four main forms of polyphenols found in green tea. Together with the alkaloids theophylline and bromine, it also contains caffeine, phenolic acids, and flavonoids. According to Wang's research, there has been a suggestion for some time that green tea polyphenols provide protection against UV-induced skin cancer. Green tea is beneficial when consumed systemically and can be used as soon as possible after exposure to protect against at least some of the biological effects of UV radiation. Green tea has a low UVB and UVA absorption rate ^[32, 33, 34].

Fig. 5: Green tea.

It stopped UVB from infiltrating leukocytes (macrophages/neutrophils), which might have produced prostaglandin (PG) metabolites and reactive oxygen species (ROS). Previous to UVB (4 MED) exposure to human skin, topical EGCG (3 mg/2.5 cm²) therapy successfully reduced UVB-induced leukocyte infiltration and lowered myeloperoxidase activity ^[35, 36].

Cucumber

Cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*) extract has a slight astringent impact in addition to its potent moisturizing properties. It also tightens skin and aids in removing dead skin cells. Cucumbers applied topically aid with burns, dermatitis, and inflamed eyes because these two acid components inhibit water retention. The invitro SPF values were determined using the methodology outlined by Mansur et al., and wavelengths between 290 and 320 nm yielded positive outcomes.

Fig. 6: Cucumber.

Grapes

Grapefruit contains sixty to seventy percent polyphenols (*Vitis vinifera*). Resveratrol is another polyphenolic phytoalexin (trans-3, 5, 4-trihydroxystilbene) found in grape skin and seeds. It functions as a potent anti-inflammatory and anti-proliferative agent and is a remarkable antioxidant^[39].

Fig. 7: Grapes.

Almonds

Almonds are the commercial name for almonds. Polyphenolic chemicals, particularly flavonoids and phenolic acids, are abundant in seeds. Testing was done on this plant's skin extract to determine its UVB protection. Following the mice's exposure to UVB radiation, alterations in glutathione levels and lipid peroxidation were examined. Applying the prepared cream topically to animals both two hours before and after radiation revealed higher glutathione and lower lipid peroxidation levels. According to the findings, topical application of the cream formulation possesses notable anti-photoaging and antioxidant capabilities^[40, 41, & 42].

Fig. 8: Almond.

Saffron:

Saffron's anti-solar activity was assessed by Gul Mohammad Zadeh SH et al. A grinder was used to dry and powder the pollen of the saffron plant (*Crocus sativus*). The lotions with 2, 4, and 8% of ground saffron, a homosalate (8%) lotion reference, and a control lotion base devoid of saffron were among the experimental compositions. As per the FDA, saffron-containing lotions were manufactured similarly to homosalate lotion reference. An in vitro spectrophotometry technique was used to calculate the sun protection factors (SPFs) of the formulations. Saffron can be employed as a natural UV absorber, according to the study's findings^[43].

Figure 9: Saffron.

Natural sunscreen oils**Shea butter (*Vitellaria paradoxa*)**

The fat from the shea nut is used to make shea butter (*Vitellaria paradoxa*). Africa's savannas are home to the shea tree. It has the ability to dissolve at body temperature, absorb quickly into the skin, and produce effects without leaving the skin feeling greasy. It is utilized as an antioxidant & has vitamins A and E in it, which both promote blood circulation beneath the skin's surface and skin cell renewal. With its cinnamic acid content, the oil offers essential defense against UV radiation that could be hazardous^[44].

Figure 10: Shea butter.

Beeswax (*Cera alba*)

Beeswax (*Cera alba*) is a naturally occurring wax that is obtained from *Apis honeybees*. Beeswax foundation is mostly used as a thickening and emulsifier, though it can also be used to stabilize emulsions. In order to make it easier to heat and mix the components of the water phase, beeswax is employed to melt the solids. Its composition of a creamy texture is its primary function^[45].

Figure 11: Beewax.

Rose water (*Damascena rose*)

Liquid-liquid extraction is used to remove it from the rose ^[46]. One of the most important qualities of their sterling sunscreen is that it has a big supply of antioxidant activities and may be used for reasons of beauty ^[47]. It is a unique source of components with promise for use in skin anti-aging therapies and functions as an emulsifying agent ^[48]

Figure 12: Rose water.

RSO stands for raspberry seed oil (*Rubusidaeus seed*).

It's the fixed oil obtained from raspberry seeds, and the pharmaceutical and cosmetic sectors highly value the fatty acid content and high vitamin A and E concentrations it contains. Its powerful antioxidant properties, together with anti-inflammatory, anti-mutagenic, anti-aging and antibacterial properties are employed in cosmetic emulsions to provide UV protection ^[49, 50]. Not only is it non-comedogenic but you may use it to hydrate your face without clogging pores ^[51]. Its sun protection properties make it advantageous for those looking for a gentle, non-irritating moisturizer with a SPF of ^[52, 53].

Figure 13: Raspberry Seed Oil.

Olive (*Olea europaea*) oil

It is an olive fruit-derived fat. Triglyceride esters of oleic and palmitic acids, as well as traces of squalene, sterols (tocosterols & phytosterols), and polyphenols such as esters of Tyrosol and hydroxyl tyrosol which include oleuropein & oleocanthal, make up olive oil. Additionally, there are some lignans and flavonoids. Olive oil has been utilized as a handy carrier for other compounds and as a home cure for skin care [54, 55, 56].

Figure 14: Olive Oil.

Coconut Oil (*Cocos nucifera*)

Indonesians cultivate and raise a large amount of the tropical plant known as coconut oil (*Cocos nucifera*) [57]. It is said to have anti-bacterial, skin barrier-repairing, wound-healing, anti-aging & moisturizing qualities in the treatment of atopic dermatitis. It also contains fatty acids and has antioxidant effects that protect against photoaging [58–64].

Figure 15: Coconut Oil.

Rosehip Seed Oil (*Rosa canina*)

It is the most abundant source of antioxidant-displaying flavonoids, polyphenols, carotenoids, and vitamin C [65, 66, 67]. Furthermore, it possesses potent antioxidant and anti-inflammatory qualities that promote collagen formation and repair [68, 69]. It functions as a moisturizer and has anti-aging qualities.

Figure 16: Rosehip Seed Oil.

Sesame Oil (*Indica sesamum*)

It has been used for thousands of years as a medicinal oil. In vitro experiments have shown that sesame oil inhibits the growth of prostaglandin and leukotrienes, as well as malignant melanoma, a type of skin cancer. It has strong antioxidant properties [68, 69]. This oil will counteract free oxygen radicals in the tissues. This oil contains palmitic, palmitoleic, stearic, oleic, linoleic & eicosenoic acids. It is the purest form of vitamin E and contains the highest concentration of sesamol, which is said to moisturize skin and maintain its suppleness [70,71,72,73].

Figure 17: Sesame Oil.

SUNSCREEN FORMULATIONS

1. EMULSION FORMULATION
2. AEROSAL FORMULATION
3. GEL FORMULATION
4. SUN STICK FORMULATION

1. Emulsion formulation

An emulsion is referred to as a lotion or cream depending on its viscosity, which ranges from 50,000 to 500,000 centipoises, offering nearly infinite versatility [74]. Typically, it is made from two incompatible liquid phases, called “water-in-oil” or “oil-in-water” emulsions. These samples are easier to spread on the skin and release from bottles [75], but they are very hard to stabilize, particularly at high temperatures [74].

2. Gel sunscreen

It is divided into 4 primary solutions: formulations that are oil anhydrous, microemulsion, hydroalcoholic, aqueous [74]. For the aqueous gel to remain transparent at all temperatures, the right amounts of water and solubilizers—such as organic agents, phosphate esters, and nonionic surfactants—must be added. Consequently, it was easy to removed by washing in water [76]. Due to their microscopic particle composition, the micro emulsion gels give off an elegant sensation and a high SPF while appearing thick, even, and smooth on the skin [77]. There are numerous similarities between the oil anhydrous recipe and ointments. On the other hand, ointments are transparent and goods made of oil anhydrous are clear. These goods can be combined to create a gel [78].

1. Aerosol sunscreens

These products are administered topically to shield skin conditions from damaging UV rays of light. They are readily rubbed onto the skin, dispersing active components in a thin layer that forms on the skin [79].

2. A sunstick

Because of its lightweight and compact design, the sun stick is without a doubt one of the most practical goods. By adding petrolatum and waxes, two primary emulsion components—oil and oil soluble components—are created to create the sun stick [74]. There are three classifications or this type of sunscreen: matte, semi-transparent, and transparent. The transparent recipe is made entirely of chemical UV filters, while the semi-transparent formula is made mostly of chemical and mineral materials, and the matte formula is made entirely of mineral sunscreen ingredients [81].

Evaluation of Sunscreen Protection by Measurement of Epidermal DNA

Synthesis:

The ability of several sunscreens to shield the cuticle from the damaging effects of UV light was examined. Changes in mouse epidermal DNA synthesis caused by ultraviolet light were utilized as a proxy for sunscreen protection. Erythroderma and edema were visually assessed simultaneously. In this first study, the main ingredient used in sunscreens to filter UV rays, paraaminobenzoic acid (PABA), was assessed. In these experiments, fluorescent sunray lamp tubes were mistreated, and epidermic DNA was extracted using hydroxylapatite. Using a recording radiometer, the amount of UV light exposure was determined. The outcomes demonstrated that the tested sunscreens could partially reverse the alterations in epidermic DNA caused by UV exposure [82].

Evaluation Parameters

Organoleptic Properties

A Brookfield viscometer was used to measure viscosity. The organoleptic property includes look and color. The pH was identified by diluting cream in water, and the result was -6.2. Pre-published methods were used to measure the spreadability of cream^[83].

Factor of Sun Protection

A UV-2000S transmittance analyzer was used to determine the sun protection factor (SPF). The polymethylmethacrylate plates with the cream were tested. The blank scan was performed using a cream foundation devoid of UV-absorbing chemicals. Three sample plates were ready, and they were cured for fifteen minutes in the dark. Subsequently, the SPF value was recorded after the plates were scanned three times^[84].

Chromatographic analysis

Chromatography techniques such as TLC, High-performance thin layer chromatography, HPLC, and gas chromatography can be used to ascertain and verify the contents of cosmetic items.

Stability analysis

For a duration of six months, it is conducted at elevated temperatures, relative humidity levels, and pH levels. All of the aforementioned parameters are routinely assessed to verify any changes in the product^[85]. The freeze-thaw technique and centrifugation were employed to evaluate the stability of every herbal sunscreen. In a freeze-thaw experiment all herbal sunscreens were held at 20°C and 40°C. Phase separation was seen after 10 minutes of centrifugation at 10,000 rpm with 500 rpm and Every test was conducted three times^[86].

Microbial Test.

The turbidity metric method or the agar well diffusion method was used for the microbial assay. It was determined that microbial growth can occur in herbal products^[87].

Physical Characteristics

Homogeneity, color, and appearance were assessed.

How to Determine Viscosity

In order to evaluate viscosity, the appropriate number of spindles was chosen for the Brookfield viscometer (RVDV-II+PRO). 50 g of formulation were kept in a 50 ml beaker spindle groove was dipped and then the rpm was adjusted at 5, 10, 20, 50 and 100 rpm, the viscosity of herbal sunscreen was tested. Using the factor derived from the reading, the viscosity was calculated.

pH determination

For measuring the pH of herbal sunscreens digital pH meter was used. 1gm of the formulation dissolved in 100ml freshly made distilled water for two hours, pH was determined. An S.D. was noted and the results were triple checked.

Extrude ability Study

By measuring the proportion of sample that extruded from the collapsible tube required to extrude at least 0.5 cm of gel ribbon in 10 seconds based on the weight in grams the extrudability of herbal sunscreens was determined in this study^[88]. Subsequently, the extrudability was calculated with the following equation:

$$\text{Extrude ability} = \text{Applied weight to extrude gel from tube (gm)} / \text{Area (cm}^2\text{)}$$

Spreadability

In skin care products, spread-ability refers to how easily a product can be applied and distributed over the skin's surface. Products with good spread-ability typically have a smooth texture and glide easily over the skin, allowing for even coverage without requiring excessive rubbing or tugging. This characteristic is important because it can enhance the user experience and ensure that the active ingredients in the product are effectively delivered to the skin. Manufacturers often formulate skincare products with ingredients and textures that optimize spreadability for better efficacy and user satisfaction^[88].

The formula for calculating Spreadability:

$$S = M \times L / t$$

Where, M = wt. tied to top of the slide

L = Length of glass slide

t = Time taken to separate the slides

Thermal Stability

The oil separation from herbal sunscreens was assessed at 37±1°C and 60–70% ambient moisture in a humidity chamber. In the 100 ml capacity flask there is 20 mm wide by 5 mm thick stripe of herbal sunscreens interior wall was covered with a lotion that reached the chamber's full height. For eight hours, beaker was kept at 37°C and 60–70% relative humidity in a humidity chamber. To pass the test, the herbal sunscreen shouldn't separate into separate oils^[89]

CONCLUSION

The main aim of this study was to develop a stable, SPF-appropriate natural sunscreen. The SPF ratings of the sunscreens containing coconut oil (F5 and F6) were found to be high—33.43 and 33.50, respectively—and to be stable, with good antioxidant activity. It has also been demonstrated that these herbal sunscreens are non-mutagenic. It may be said that the current research will hopefully result in better ways to treat sunburns brought on by exposure to UV light. The study also shows that the most effective, reliable, and repeatable method for assessing the efficacy of herbal sunscreens is UV Spectroscopy. Chemicals have long been a common ingredient in sunscreen formulations as a photo protective agent. Their negative consequences are making them less common these days.

REFERENCE

1. Hidaka, H.; Horikoshi, S.; Serpone, N.; Knowland, J. In vitro photochemical damage to DNA, RNA and their bases by an inorganic sunscreen agent on exposure to UVA and UVB radiation. *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A Chem.* 1997, 111, 205–213. [CrossRef].
2. D'Orazio, J.; Jarrett, S.; Amaro-Ortiz, A.; Scott, T. UV radiation and the skin. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 2013, 14, 12222–12248. [CrossRef] [PubMed].
3. Juzeniene, A.; Moan, J. Beneficial effects of UV radiation other than via vitamin D production. *Dermato-Endocrinol.* 2011 4, 109–117. [CrossRef] [PubMed].
4. Bintsis, T.; Litopoulou-Tzanetaki, E.; Davies, R.; Robinson, R.K. The antimicrobial effects of long-wave ultra-violet light and furocoumarins on some micro-organisms that occur in cheese brines. *Food Microbiol.* 2000, 17, 687–695. [CrossRef].
5. Fleury, N.; Geldenhuys, S.; Gorman, S. Sun exposure and its effects on human health: Mechanisms through which sun exposure could reduce the risk of developing obesity and cardiometabolic dysfunction. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 2016, 13, 999. [CrossRef].
6. Weller, R.B. Sunlight has cardiovascular benefits independently of vitamin D. *Blood Purif.* 2016, 41, 130–134. [CrossRef].
7. Taylor, B.R. Ultraviolet radiation and the eye: An epidemiologic study. *Tr. Am. Ophth. Soc.* 1989, 87, 802.2)
8. IARC working group on the evaluation of cancer-preventive agents in sunscreens. In: *IARC Handbooks of Cancer Prevention*. Lyon: IARC (2001). p. 1–193.
9. Administration, Australian Government Department of Health Therapeutic Goods (August 30, 2019).
10. "Australian Regulatory Guidelines for Sunscreens (ARGS)". Therapeutic Goods Administration (TGA). Retrieved July 26, 2021.]
11. Boyd AS, Naylor M, Cameron GS, et al. The effects of chronic sunscreen use on the histologic changes of dermatoheliosis. *J Am AcadDermatol.* Dec 1995; 33(6):941-6 .
12. Fotiades J, Soter NA and Lim HW. Results of evaluation of 203 patients for photosensitivity in a 7.3- year period. *J Am AcadDermatol.* Oct 1995; 33(4):597-602.
13. DeBuys HV, Levy SB, Murray JC, et al. Modern approaches to photo protection. *DermatolClin.* Oct 2000; 18(4):577-90.
14. Diffey BL and Grice J. The influence of sunscreen type on photo protection. *Br J Dermatol.* Jul 1997; 137(1):103-5.
15. Dromgoole SH and Maibach HI. Sunscreening agent intolerance: contact and photo contact sensitization and contact urticaria. *J Am AcadDermatol.* Jun 1990; 22(6):1068-78.
16. Miss. Waghmode Monika VasantProf.Khade. P. Dr. HINGANE L.D. ADITYA PHARMACY COLLEGE, BEED 431122, "Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Sunscreen Cream", 2021 IJCRT , Volume 9, Issue 12, ISSN: 2320-2882,2021.
17. PappireddyLahari, K.V. Ratnamala, "Formulation Development and Evaluation of Sunscreen", IJIRT, Volume 8 Issue 1, ISSN: 2349-6002, June 2021.
18. Sahu RK, Roy A, Kushwah P, Khare M, Mudotiya R. Formulation and development of whitening polyherbal face cream. *Research Journal of Topical and Cosmetic Science.* 2012; 3(1): 23-27.

19. Sahu RK, Roy A, Jha AK, Dwivedi J. Promotion and computation of inhibitory effect on tyrosinase activity of herbal cream by incorporating indigenous medicinal plants. *Pakistan Journal of Biological Sciences*. 2014; 17(1): 146-150.
20. Kavanaugh EE (September 11, 1998). "Re: Tentative Final Monograph for OTC Sunscreen" (PDF). Cosmetic, Toiletry, and Fragrance Association. Retrieved September 25, 2009.
21. JKlein, K. Sunscreen products: Formulation and regulatory considerations. *Cosmet. Sci. Technol. Ser.* 1997, 285–312. [Google Scholar]
22. Schalka S, dos Reis VM, Cucé LC () August 2009). "The influence of the amount of sunscreen applied and its sun protection factor (SPF): evaluation of two sunscreens including the same ingredients at different concentrations". *Photodermatology, Photoimmunology&Photomedicine*. 25 (4): 175–80. doi:10.1111/ j.1600-0781.2009.00408.x. PMID 19614894. S2CID 38250220.
23. Vogler BK, Ernst E; Aloe vera: A systematic review of its clinical effectiveness. *British Journal of General Practice*, 1999; 49(447): 823–828.
24. West DP, Zhu YF; Evaluation of Aloe vera gel gloves in the treatment of dry skin associatedwith occupational exposure. *American Journal of infection control*, 2003; 31(1): 40–42.
25. Rajpal V; Aloe barbadensis Mill/A. veraTourn ex linn. In *Standardization of botanicals testing and extraction methods of medicinal herbs*.Vol. 1,Easternpublishers,New Delhi, 2000: 25.
26. Daud FS, Kulkarni SB; Comparative evaluation of photo protective effect of aloe veraTourn. ex. linn on UV damage in different Asian hair types. *Indian Journal of Natural Products and Resources*, 2011; 2(2): 179-183.
27. Sahasrabuddhe S; Lycopene-An Antioxidant. *Pharma Times*, 2011, 43(12): 13-15.
28. Stahl W, Heinrich U, Aust O, Tronnier H, Sies H; Lycopene-rich products and dietary photo protection.*Photochemical&Photobiological Sciences*, 2006;5:238-242.
29. Lycopene. Available from www.natural facts\lycopene.html .
30. Basu A, Penugonda K; Pomegranate juice: a heart-healthy fruit juice. *Nutrition Reviews*, 2009; 67(1): 49–56.
31. Weerakkody P, Jobling J, Infante MMV, Rogers G; The effect of maturity, sunburn and the application of sunscreens on the internal and external qualities of pomegranate fruit grown in Australia. *ScientiaHorticulturae*, 2010; 124: 57-61.
32. Yang C, Wang Z; Tea and cancer. *Journal of the National Cancer Institute*, 1993; 85(13): 1038–1049.
33. Lu Y-P, Lou Y-R, Xie J-G, et al; Topical applications of caffeine or (-)- epigallocatechingallate (EGCG) inhibit carcinogenesisand selectively increase apoptosis in UVB-induced skin tumors in mice. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 2002; 99(19): 12455-12460.
34. Wang Z, Agarwal R, Bickers D, Mukhtar H; Protection against ultraviolet B radiationinducedphotocarcinogenesis in hairless mice by green tea polyphenols. *Carcinogenesis*, 1991; 12(8): 1527-1530.
35. Yarnell E, Kathy A,Herbal Sunscreens and Ultraviolet Protectants. *Alternative andcomplementary therapies*, 2012; 18(3): 141-144.
36. Katiyar SK, Elmets CA, Agarwal R, Mukhtar H; Protection against ultraviolet-B radiationinduced local and systemic suppression of contact hypersensitivity and edema responses in C3H/HeN mice by green tea polyphenols. *Photochemistry and Photobiology*, 1995; 62: 855-861.
37. Hogade MG, Patil BS, Dhumal P; Comparative sun protection factordetermination of fresh fruits extract ofCucumbers marketed cosmetic formulation. *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and ChemicalSciences*, 2010; 1(3): 55-59.
38. Ashawant MS, Saraf S and Swarnlata S; Comparative sun protection factor determination of fresh Aloe vera gel vs marketed formulation. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Education and Research*, 2008; 42(4): 319-322.
39. Deore SL, Kombade S, Baviskar BA, Khadabadi SS. Photoprotective antioxidant phytochemicals. *International Journal of Phytopharmacy*, 2012; 2(3): 72-76.
40. Kim YH, Yang HE, Park BK, Heo MY, Jo BK, Kim HP; The extract of the flowers of *Prunuspersica*, a new cosmetic ingredient protects against solar ultraviolet–induced skin damage in vivo. *Journal of Cosmetic Science*, 2002; 53(1); 27-34.
41. Wijeratne SS, Abou-zaid MM, Shahidi F; Antioxidant polyphenols in almonds and its coproducts.*Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 2006; 54 (2); 312-318.
42. Sachdeva MK and Katyal T. Abatement of detrimental effects of photo aging by *Prunusamygdalus* skin extract. *International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Research*, 2011; 3(1), 57-59.
43. Patil VV, Patil SB, Kondawar MS, Naikwade NS, Magdum CS; Study of methanolic extract of flower of *Spathodeacampanulata* L. as an anti-solar. *International Journal of Green Pharmacy*, 2009; 3(3): 248-249.
44. Golmohammadzadeh SH, MR Jaafari MR, Hosseinzadeh H; Does Saffron Have Antisolar and Moisturizing Effects? *Iranian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2010; 9(2): 133-140.
45. Natural sunscreen Available from <http://wakeup-world.com/2012/05/14/naturalsunscreen/>.
46. Erbaş S, Baydar H. Variation in scent compounds of oil-bearing Rose (*Rosa damascene* Mill.) Produced by headspace solid Phase micro-extraction, hydrodistillation and solvent extraction. *Rec. Nat. Prod.* 2016; 10: 5555- 565.
47. Balakrishnan KP, Aswamy NN. Botanicals as sunscreens: Their role in the prevention of photoaging and skin cancer. *Int. J. Res. Cosmet. Sci.* 2011; 1: 1-12.
48. Sun L, Zhang Y, Zhuang Y. Antiphotaging Effect and Purification of an Antioxidant Peptide from *Tilapia (OreochromisNiloticus)* Gelatin Peptides. *J. Funct. Foods*. 2013; 5: 154–162. [CrossRef]
49. Snyder SM, Low RM, Stocks JC, Eggett DL, Parker TL. Juice, Pulp and Seeds Fractionated from Dry Climate Primocane Raspberry Cultivars (*Rubusidaeus*) Have Significantly Different Antioxidant Capacity, Anthocyanin Content and Color. *Plant Foods Hum. Nutr.* 2012; 67: 358–364. [CrossRef]

50. Oomah BD, Ladet S, Godfrey DV, Liang J, Girard B. Characteristics of raspberry (*Rubusidaeus L.*) seed oil. *Food Chem.* 2000; 69: 187–193. [CrossRef]
51. Ryan AS, Goldsmith LA. Nutrition and the skin. *Clin. Dermatol.* 1996; 14: 389–406. [CrossRef]
52. Gašperlin M, Gosenca M. Main approaches for delivering antioxidant vitamins through the skin to prevent skin ageing. *Expert Opin. Drug Deliv.* 2011; 8: 905–919. [CrossRef]
53. Lee J, Jiang S, Levine N, Watson RR. Carotenoid supplementation reduces erythema in human skin after simulated solar radiation exposure. *Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. Med.* 2000; 223: 170–174. [CrossRef]
54. Kole P, Jadhav H, Thakur P. Cosmetics Potential of Herbal Extracts. *Nat. Prod. Radiance.* 2005; 4(4): 315-321.
55. Gediya S, Mistry R, Patel U, Blessy M. Herbal Plants Used as a Cosmetics. *Scholars Research Library.* 2011; 1(1):24-32.
56. Ashawat M, Shailendra S, Swarnalata S. Biochemical and Histopathological Studies of Herbal Cream against UV Radiation Induced Damage. *Trend Med. Res.* 2007; 2(3): 135-141.
57. DebMandal, M. &Mandal, S. 2011. Coconut (*Cocosnucifera L.* Arecaceae): In health promotion and disease prevention. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Medicine* 4(3): 241-247.
58. Nevin, K. G. &Rajamohan, T. 2010. Effect of topical application of virgin coconut oil on skin components and anti-oxidant status during dermal wound healing in young rats. *Skin Pharmacology and Physiology* 23(6): 290- 297.
59. Merlin Hernanto, Suswardana, PutuDyahAyuSaraswati, SunardiRadiono 2008. Virgin coconut oil protection against UVB induced erythema and pigmentation. *BerkalaIlmuKesehatanKulit&Kelamin* 20(3): 208-211.
60. Kim, S. , Jang, J. E. , Kim, J. , Lee, Y. I. , Lee, D. W. , Song, S. Y. & Lee, J. H. 2017. Enhanced barrier functions and antiinflammatory effect of cultured coconut extract on human skin. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 106(Part A): 367-375.
61. Rahmad, R. ,Earlia, N. , Nabila, C. , Inayati, I. , Amin, M. , Prakoeswa, C. R. S. , Khairan, K. &Idroes, R. 2019. Antibacterial cream formulation of ethanolicPliiek U extracts and ethanolic residue hexane Pliiek U extracts against *Staphylococcus aureus*. In *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* 523. Acheh: IOP Publishing. p. 012011.
62. Lin, T. K. ,Zhong, L. & Santiago, J. 2017. Anti-inflammatory and skin barrier repair effects of topical application of some plant oils. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 19(1): 70.
63. Vaughn, A. R. , Clark, A. K. , Sivamani, R. K. & Shi, V. Y. 2018. Natural oils for skin-barrier repair: Ancient compounds now backed by modern science. *American Journal of Clinical Dermatology* 19(1): 103-117.
64. Evangelista, M. T. P. , Abad-Casintahan, F. & Lopez-Villafuerte, L. 2014. The effect of topical virgin coconut oil on SCORAD index, transepidermal water loss, and skin capacitance in mild to moderate pediatric atopic dermatitis: A randomized, double-blind, clinical trial. *International Journal of Dermatology* 53(1): 100-108.
65. Halvorsen BL, Holte K, Myhrstad MCV, et al. A systematic screening of total antioxidants in dietary plants. *J Nutr.* 2002;132:461–471. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
66. Patel S. Rose hips as complementary and alternative medicine: overview of the present status and prospects. *Med J Nutrition Metab.* 2013;6:89–97. [Google Scholar]
67. Fan C, Pacier C, Martirosyan DM. Rose hip (*Rosa canina L.*): a functional food perspective. *Funct Foods Health Dis.* 2014;4(11):493–509. [Google Scholar]
68. Larsen E, Kharazmi A, Christensen LP, Christensen SB. An antiinflammatorygalactolipid from rose hip (*Rosa canina*) that inhibits chemotaxis of human peripheral blood neutrophils in vitro. *J Nat Prod.* 2003;66(7):994– 995. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
69. Schwager J, Hoeller U, Wolfram S, Richard N. Rose hip and its constituent galactolipids confer cartilage protection by modulating cytokine, and chemokine expression. *BMC Complement Altern Med.* 2011;11:105– 119. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
70. Anitha T. , Medicinal Plants used in Skin Protection, *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research.* 2012; 5(3):35-38.
71. Pandey S, Meshya N, Viral D. Herbs Play an Important Role in the Field of Cosmetics. *International Journal of Pharm Tech Research.* 2010; 1(1): 632-639.
72. Rangari VD. Traditional Drugs of India. *Pharmacognosy and phytochemistry carrier Publication Nashik* 2003; 2(1) 225-267.
73. Khandelwal KR *Practical Pharmacognosy Techniques and Experimental.* NiraliPrakashan Pune 2004; (12):149- 156.
74. Klein, K. Sunscreen products: Formulation and regulatory considerations. *Cosmet. Sci. Technol. Ser.* 1997, 285–312. [Google Scholar]
75. Schröder, B.; Ohrmann, R.; Issleib, M.; Endlein, E. O/W-Emulsifiers, O/W-Emulsions and Methods of Manufacture Thereof. US8961943B2, 24 February 2015. [Google Scholar]
76. Bara, I.; Mellul, M. New Cosmetic or Dermopharmaceutical Compositions in the Form of Aqueous Gels Modified by the Addition of Expanded Microspheres. U.S. Patent 5593680, 14 January 1997. [Google Scholar]
77. Diec, K.H.; Gersbarlag, H.; Klier, M.; Schreiber, J.; Wolf, F. Cosmetic or Dermatological Gels Based on Microemulsions. U.S. Patent 6607733B1, 19 August 2003. [Google Scholar]
78. Strobridge, J.R. Gel-Type Sunscreen Composition. U.S. Patent 4917882, 17 April 1990. [Google Scholar]
79. Hougaz, L. Sunscreen Aerosol Spray. U.S. Patent 20090061001A1, 5 March 2009. [Google Scholar] 33. Lee, S.-H. New Technical Developments in Sun Care and Blue Light Defense; SUNJIN Beauty Science: Gyeonggi-do, Korea, 2018; p. 134. [Google Scholar] .
80. Klein, K. Sunscreen products: Formulation and regulatory considerations. *Cosmet. Sci. Technol. Ser.* 1997, 285–312. [Google Scholar]
81. Mithal BM and Saha RNA. Hand book of cosmetics, first edition, reprint-2007, VallabhPrakashan, Delhi 122-124.

82. Berneburg M, Plettenberg H, Medve-König K, et al. Induction of the photo aging-associated mitochondrial common deletion in vivo in normal human skin. *J Invest Dermatol*, 2004,
83. Shishikura Y, Khokhar S. Factors affecting the levels of catechins and caffeine in tea beverage: estimated daily intakes and antioxidant activity. *J Sci Food Agric*. 2005;85:2125–2133. [Google Scholar]
84. Lin YS, Tsai YJ, Tsay JS, Lin JK. Factors affecting the levels of tea polyphenols and caffeine in tea leaves. *J Agric Food Chem*. 2003;51:1864–1873.
85. Kale S, Kavade E, Uadav AV. Formulation and in-vitro evaluation for sun protection factor of *Crinum asiaticum* linn flower Extract Sunscreen Creams. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Education and Research* 2012;46(2):112-119.
86. Bouwstra JA, Gooris GS, Dubbelaar FE, Ponc M. Cholesterol sulfate and calcium affect stratum corneum lipid organization over a wide temperature range. *J Lipid Res*. 1999;40(12):2303-12.
87. Gomma YA, Darwish IA, Boraei NA. Formulation of wax oxybenzonemicroparticles using a factorial approach. *Journal of Microencapsulation* 2010;27(7):628-639.
88. Saifee M, Atre M, Toshiwal R. Formulation and In-vitro Evaluation of Ethosomal Gel of Repaglinide for Transdermal Delivery. *Int J Pharm Phytopharmacol Res*. 2021;11(4):11-7. doi:10.51847/IQKgwU11
89. Shakib Z, Shahraki N, Razavi BM, Hosseinzadeh H. Aloe vera as an herbal medicine in the treatment of metabolic syndrome: A review. *Phytother Res*. 2019;33(10):2649-60. doi:10.1002/ptr.6465

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